

The basic stages of the technical and physical preparations that reduce the risk of injuries in swimming

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Abstract

The paper presents the issue of the basic stages that prepare a swimmer for physical effort and help to reduce the risk of injuries. A swimming pool is represented as one of the safest places to practice sport, due to the physical properties of water and the lack of a typical contact with other swimmers. Unfortunately, because of the constant repetition of the same movements, swimmers are prone to strain lesions and microinjuries, which affect their joints and muscles. The paper pays particular attention to the importance of training, which should be performed not only in a pool but also at a gym. Increasing endurance and muscular strength is extremely important due to the reduction of the injury risk. Moreover, it should be stressed that a proper swimming technique is also essential for safety. Correct performance of the movements makes the muscles work effectively and economically, thus reducing the likelihood of overstraining the muscles and joints. The author also analysed the literature concerning the influence of warm-up and stretching exercises on the human body before intense effort; however, the available study results do not offer an unambiguous answer. However, it should be kept in mind that, by developing and improving a swimming technique, the sport will provide a lot of satisfaction and will be suitable for a wide range of people – from professionals, through children, to patients.

Keywords: swimming, injuries, warm-up

Introduction

Swimming is a type of sport practiced by various groups of people, including individuals spending time at a swimming pool for recreational purposes, patients taking advantage of the water environment for rehabilitation and those who perform this physical activity on a competitive basis. Swimming is generally considered to be a sport of very low injury risk. The physical properties of water make it a conducive environment for physical activity. The surrounding water protects people against the potential negative impact of gravitational force or inertia, and the pure nature of most water sports can be described as contactless. Nevertheless, individuals who practice competitive swimming, especially over a longer period, are vulnerable to the adverse effects of participating in this type of sporting activity, which are primarily related to joint and muscle strain lesions. Common complaints experienced by athletes involved in this type of physical activity include problems with the shoulders, the knees or the lumbar section of the spinal column. For this reason, great weight should be given to out-of-water training, for instance at a gym or in a sports hall. The type of exercises performed, both in the water and at a gym, may be similar. However, the latter may be enriched by typical activities aimed at strengthening and increasing

the endurance of muscles. This is also of considerable importance while working on a proper swimming technique. The subject that proved to be problematic was the aspect of warm-up and stretching exercises, which have always been practiced, despite the lack of clear scientific evidence supporting their positive effects. Authors of numerous studies presented divergent and sometimes even contradictory results, which made it impossible to unambiguously determine the influence of this type of exercises on the human body.

1. The most common injuries

As noted above, the water environment is considered to be exceptionally safe. While assessing the risk of injury, it is also important to take account of its surrounding. It is absolutely necessary to take particular care while moving around the swimming pool area due to the risk of slipping and falling. During the swimming activity itself, it is extremely rare for swimmers to sustain serious injuries, namely as a result of hitting their head or upper and lower limbs against the wall of the pool or jumping into too shallow water. The most frequent injuries include joint and muscle strain lesions [1]. The American Academy of Pediatrics indicated four essential, negative changes

that may occur after practicing this sport over a longer period (Table 1).

A single training session generates thousands of cyclical, repeated movements of the upper limb. The shoulder joint is made up of the following parts: the glenohumeral and scapular joint, the acromioclavicular joint, the scapulothoracic joint, the sternoclavicular joint and the subacromial space. Each of these structures may be the cause of pain in the entire shoulder and lead to significant limitations of mobility. The preferred swimming front-stroke position, in which the arms keep moving forward, may lead to muscular contractures in the glenohumeral joint. After a certain time, this may force a posture in which the person looks as if s/he was constantly stooping, because the shoulders are pulled and rounded to the front, with the cervical spine being slightly bent forward. In advanced cases, this may even lead to a shift in the body's centre of gravity.

The most common swimming injuries affect the upper limbs – the shoulders and the elbows, as well as the surrounding muscles. In the case of the lower limbs, they affect the knees [3, 4].

The flip-turns performed when you swim, involving appropriate force to push against the surface of the wall, have a negative impact on the knee joints. This activity is comparable to doing partial squats. It is particularly visible in individuals who prefer the breast stroke – or the so-called “frog” swimming style. Regular bending of knees and intense pushing movements pose a risk of overstraining these joints. In this respect, it must be underlined that individuals specialising in breaststroke often do addition-

al exercises at a gym, with a view to strengthening the lower limb muscles. These movements imitate those performed in the water – squats or jump squats. Overdoing this type of exercise may negatively affect the condition of knee joints.

People who practice swimming suffer from spinal pain very rarely. It mostly affects beginners who are just starting their adventure with this type of sport, without yet mastering the proper swimming technique. The pain and discomfort are most often localised in the cervical and thoracic spine, as well as in the dorsal muscles at the lumbar section. An improper swimming technique in the front-stroke position, unnatural, rapid and ill-performed rotational movements of the upper body may easily result in muscle strain or injuries in the above-mentioned parts of the body.

Swimming often forces a long-term horizontal position – like in the case of lying on the front of the body. In such a situation, the postural muscles can be easily weakened, because they basically perform no work in this position. Therefore, it is extremely important to implement additional training outside a swimming pool, which will boost the muscular corset and help to avoid the potential undesired effects.

No complaint that emerges during swimming activities or after the end of training should be downplayed. It should always be specially noted whether the health condition raises no concerns, because no treatment for even a minor complaint could have serious consequences (Table 2).

Tab. 1. The injuries occurring in swimmers [2].

Condition	Description	Treatment
Swimmer's shoulder	A compression or “impingement” of the rotator cuff tendons caused by repetitive overhead shoulder arcs. Overdevelopment of chest muscles and weak back muscles with progressive muscle fatigue can lead to this injury.	Treatment is individualized and must address all contributing factors. Most treatment plans include some form of physical therapy to learn correct posture and exercises to strengthen shoulder blade muscles. Although common for swimmers to do, excessive stretching of the shoulder muscles is not recommended.
Low back pain	Caused by repetitive turns, rotations, and extended back positions. Common causes include muscle strains, joint irritation and, in rare cases, stress fractures. Proper diagnosis by a doctor is essential to ensure the appropriate treatment recommendations are made. X-rays or other testing may be needed	Treatment usually is rest, medicines, and physical therapy to include core (abdominal, hips, and low back) strengthening exercises.
Breaststroker's knee	A chronic sprain of the medial collateral ligament on the inside of the knee related to the frog kick in breaststroke. Kneecap pain (patellofemoral pain) is also common due to other forms of kicking.	Treatment is to rest from these types of kicks.
Foot and ankle injuries	Occur from repetitive flutter and dolphin kicking. This places the toes and ankle in an extreme pointed position that strains the top of the foot and causes pain.	Treatment is rest, ice, medicines, and strengthening exercises.

Tab 2. Complaints that may occur in swimmers [2].

Condition	Prevention/Treatment
Swimmer's ear	Swimmers should use tight-fitting swim caps that cover the ears. They should see a doctor if symptoms of ear pain and/or drainage develop. Swimmer's ear is usually treated with cleaning, antibiotic drops, and 3 to 10 days out of the pool. Acetic acid drops may help prevent swimmer's ear.
Pinkeye	Symptoms may be caused by irritation from chlorine and other chemicals, but viral and/or bacterial eye infections are highly contagious. Swimmers should see a doctor. Treatment includes prescription antibiotic eye drops and 3 to 7 days out of the pool.
Athlete's foot and plantar warts	Swimmers should wear sandals on pool decks and locker room floors to help prevent foot infections. Cuts on the foot should be examined by a doctor.
Exercise-induced asthma	Swimmers with asthma vary greatly in their symptoms. Some do better in the warm, humid environment while others do not. Some find heavily chlorinated pools make symptoms worse. Asthma should not limit participation and performance of swimmers. Every swimmer should have a personal asthma action plan. Asthmatic swimmers can prevent episodes by taking their medicines and using an inhaler before practices or meets. Inhalers and spacers should always be on hand during activity. Swimmers should stop swimming and see a doctor if they have difficulty breathing while swimming.
Overtraining (excessive fatigue)	This is common in swimmers because of year-round swimming and training. Treatment includes medical and nutritional evaluation and rest from swimming during noncompetition seasons.

2. The training of swimmers

The development of muscular strength is essential for a swimmer, hence the importance of training at a gym. Its form can be partially similar to the exercises performed in the water, but it also contains elements of typical strength training, e.g. with a load. It is worth emphasising that the weight of a given load should always be selected so that it can be lifted to properly perform the exercise. It is better to carry out several repetitions in a proper manner than to perform a series of improper movements. This applies to both the starting position and the exercise itself [5]. Faulty postures, too, are a common problem. Poor posture not only looks terrible and increases chances for a whole host of injuries, but it can actually mess with stroke technique. For instance, decreased shoulder range of motion resulting from tight chest and shoulder muscles decreases stroke length and strength. What matters in each type of training is not the quantity, but rather the quality. Exercise done in a hurry and inaccurately can have the opposite effect of the one desired. Training activities must be designed individually for each person, and based on systematicity and gradual application of the load [6]. Unfortunately, muscle strength and endurance are quite difficult and time-consuming to develop, and when the training activities are ceased, they easily and quickly fade away. Therefore, a great deal of emphasis is placed on regular exercise. It should also be borne in mind that a short yet highly intense training will not always be effective.

The exercise must be properly spread over time and characterised by appropriate intensity.

Figure 1 presents the most important muscles that should be strengthened at a gym (Fig.1).

The first training sessions often cause discomfort and slight pain in those muscles, because strength exercises may lead to certain muscle fibres being torn, thus developing microinjuries. These sensations usually pass within two days.

Muscles take approximately 48 hours to regenerate and therefore strength exercise should be performed not more frequently than every second day. The majority of training programmes for swimmers contain several different stages. Depending on the phase, emphasis is placed on endurance, speed or strength. Table 3 presents an example of a training (early-season).

It should be remembered that there is no single effective and universal training plan, which would be suitable for all. Every single person is different, exhibits various levels of physical fitness and different resilience of the body to training stimuli, and hence to the rate of progress. Therefore, it is essential to learn to observe your body and properly interpret and react to the signals it sends. In the event of alarming signs, it is necessary to consult a physician, a qualified trainer or a physiotherapist [9].

There is a tremendous variety of exercises that can help us strengthen the muscles. As a result, it is possible to diversify the training to avoid monotony.

Fig. 1. Examples of muscles that should be strengthened during gym workout [7].

Tab3. An example of an early-season training for swimmers [8].

Exercise	Muscles	Week 1	Week 2	Week 3	Week 4
Incline Hammer Strength Chest Press	Chest, shoulders, triceps,	3x12	3x15	3x20	3x25
Standing Pull Downs	Latissimus dorsi, biceps, middle back, shoulders	3x12	3x15	3x20	3x25
Narrow Grip Seated Row	Middle back, biceps, latissimus dorsi, shoulders,	3x12	3x15	3x20	3x25
Seated Shoulder Raises	Back,	3x12	3x15	3x20	3x25
One Arm Standing Tricep Press	Triceps, shoulders,	3x12	3x15	3x20	3x25
Seated One Arm Curls	Biceps,	3x12	3x15	3x20	3x25
Wide Grip Lat Pull Downs	Middle back, biceps, latissimus dorsi, shoulders,	3x12	3x15	3x20	3x25
Step Ups	Quadriceps, calves, glutes, hamstrings,	3x12	3x15	3x20	3x25
Seated Quad Extensions	Quadriceps,	3x12	3x15	3x20	3x25
Hamstring Curls	Hamstring,	3x12	3x15	3x20	3x25
Seated Independent Calf Press	Calves,	3x12	3x15	3x20	3x25
Seated Leg Press	Quadriceps, calves, glutes, hamstrings.	3x12	3x15	3x20	3x25

It is also worth noting the advantages of exercising in the water environment. In his study, Tanaka Hirofumi examined whether regular swimming can lower blood pressure and thus influence the reduction of arterial hypertension. The results obtained confirmed his hypothesis. The paper also stresses the clinical significance of this result, because a swimming pool can constitute an alternative to standard exercises and may be offered to hypertensive, obese or orthopedic patients [10]. This helps to encourage individuals suffering from the above-

mentioned conditions to take up physical activity, because swimming is not merely the domain of the young and healthy people.

3. The role of warm-up

Warm-up is defined as an activity performing two important functions, namely: it improves the dynamics of muscles to make them less vulnerable to injuries and it prepares athletes for the requirements of the planned

physical activity. It has been proved that even a one-degree increase in muscle temperature has an influence on a statistically significant prolongation of the maximum working time of hind leg muscles in laboratory animals [11]. It is believed that a well performed warm-up should produce a mild sweat without fatiguing the individual. Based on its nature, warm-up can be divided into two types: passive and active [12]. Active warm up can, in turn, be classified as general and specific. Passive warm-up involves an increase in the muscle or internal body temperature as a result of providing energy from external sources, such as a sauna or hot compresses [12, 13]. General warm-up is considered to encompass each non-specific type of physical activity, including jogging or cycling [12, 13, 14]. Specific warm-up involves activation and stretching of the muscles in a manner that is typical for a given sport [13, 14]. It seems that the most effective form of warm-up is the specific variant, because it imitates the manner in which the muscles work during the planned physical activity [14, 15].

Stretching is commonly used during warm-up before each type of physical activity. However, its influence on the subsequent performance and injury prevention is not fully known. There are numerous studies indicating that even single stretching exercises can severely affect muscle strength and, to a lesser extent, also weaken muscle power. The scope for the effects of stretching exercise combined with other warm-up components is also unknown. There is a limited number of works that present inconclusive results concerning the influence of stretching exercise on injury prevention. A general conclusion could be drawn that stretching combined with warm-up has no influence on strain injuries. There is evidence showing that stretching influences the incidence of muscle strain. However, there is need for further examination of this issue.

In the literature, we can distinguish several studies that analysed the dependency between pre participation stretching and the risk of injury. The justification for carrying out those studies is the fact that this type of warm-up is commonly used before participating in various kinds of physical activity. It also seems interesting to note that so far no consideration has been given as to why stretching could influence the risk of injuries. It is believed that stretching can have a larger impact on certain types of injuries compared to others [16]. The authors of the works present a theory, explaining the rationale for stretching before physical activities:

☐ stretching makes the muscle-tendon unit more compliant[17, 18, 20],

☐ increased compliance shifts the angle-torque relationship to allow greater relative force production at longer muscle lengths [19, 20],

☐ subsequently the enhanced ability to resist excessive muscle elongation may decrease the susceptibility to a muscle strain injury[16].

On the other hand, a substantial part of the literature indicates that the risk of injuries can be lowered by a well performed warm-up which prepares the body for physical effort. There is an increase in flexibility, which in turn helps to improve effectiveness in the water. It is also highlighted that, in the case of warm-up in the water, our body will quickly cool down and therefore emphasis should be placed on marching, running and swinging the upper and lower limbs between the stretching exercises [11, 13, 21, 22]. Some study results indicate, on the other hand, that warm-up has an influence neither on the reduction of injury risk nor on the improvement of how the components of a given sport are performed [23, 24, 25, 26].

The subject of warm-up and stretching exercise is an issue that should be more deeply explored. The results presented by the authors of the studies are very diverse and provide no clear answer.

4. The influence of a swimming technique

A swimming technique is of major importance. Every year, a large number of swimmers seek assistance from physicians and physiotherapists due to shoulder pain or injury. They try to eliminate the consequence, not always realising the cause of the problem, which may reside in an improper swimming technique. In 9 out of 10 cases, the manner of jumping into a swimming pool is linked to the presence of shoulder pain.

Not everybody, however, is aware that they swim incorrectly. Even if somebody else makes a relevant remark, it is not always possible to improve the given aspect by analysing that person's words. The best method is to film yourself while you jump, swim and flip-turn. As soon as we see what and when should be corrected, it will be easier to do it in a pool. Improving the technique is not difficult in itself. However, it is necessary to know what to pay special attention to. The effort put in the improvement of swimming quality will surely be rewarded.

Body rotation and the moment of hand insertion under water are particularly significant. The key to avoid discomfort and pain in the shoulder joint is to develop a proper, symmetrical turn (rotation) of the body through the bilateral breathing pattern. Swimming with a flat body in the water with limited rotation along the long axis of the spine causes the arms to swing around the side during the recovery phase. This swinging action results in large amounts of internal rotation at the shoulder joint which is the major source of impingement and rotator cuff issues. A hand placed in internal rotation, in which the thumb enters the water first, also leads to excessive internal

rotation in the shoulder joint. Assuming that there are approximately 3,200 such movements within an hour of swimming, this may eventually cause severe pain as well as an injury due to overstraining the joint. Instead of dipping the thumb into water first, it is necessary to modify the technique in such a manner that water entry is made with the fingertips, with the whole palm of the hand.

A faulty body posture, as mentioned earlier, is of the utmost importance. If, during everyday activities, the position of our body is incorrect, it will also affect the manner in which our muscles work in a swimming pool, thus increasing the risk of overstraining and injuries. It is necessary to underline the importance of improving the elasticity of the muscles in the front part of the shoulder joint and in the chest. Combined with exercises to increase the stability of the rear arm muscles, it can have a positive influence on both the swimming technique and the body posture.

Typically swimmers will pull through with either a dropped elbow or with a very straight arm. Doing so loads the shoulder muscles excessively as the majority of the pull through phase is spent pushing down, rather than pressing back.

Working to develop a high elbow catch technique with enhanced swimming posture will really help you utilise the larger, more powerful muscle groups of your chest and upper back, rather than rely upon the shoulders.

The improvement of the body posture and position during the swimming activity means that the power needed for the movement is utilised as effectively and efficiently as possible [27].

Conclusions:

Despite that fact that the water environment is safe for practicing sport, it should be remembered that injuries may occur not only as a result of falling, hitting or unexpected contact with another person. Swimmers most often struggle with strain lesions within joints and muscles. Observing the rules of proper training in the water and at a gym, as well as taking care of its proper performance, will reduce the risk of undesirable effects. A good swimming technique will have the following factors in place, consistently: bilateral breathing for at least 80% of your training sessions, symmetrical body rotation, hand entry into the water with fingertip first, not thumb, avoiding midline cross over at the front of the stroke, developing and maintaining of good upper body posture and targeting a high elbow catch and pull through.

It is worthwhile looking at the issue of warm-up and stretching exercises. Unfortunately, the available literature does not fully explain their role and influence. The studies conducted by various authors present contradictory results, stating that warm-up and stretching have a

positive, negative or no influence at all. It is essential also due to the fact that warm-up was recommended before each physical activity of high intensity to, among other things, avoid injuries, and a considerable part of the studies indicate that stretching exercises increase the risk of some injuries. This subject certainly requires further examination.

Developing and improving one's skills will make swimming a highly satisfactory experience. At the same time, by strengthening the muscles and paying attention to proper performance of the particular components of the swimming technique, the risk of potential injuries will be reduced.

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Conflict of interest:

The authors have declared no conflict of interest.